

HOUSEHOLD QUESTIONNAIRE

Instructions

- This questionnaire must be completed with information provided by the household head of the selected households. If the household head is not present, ask for another adult (must be 18 years or older) who can answer the questionnaire.
- Make sure that you explain the informed consent model, and how study results are reported to LGUs.
- No question will remain unanswered without justification.
- Do not read out questions loudly and instead try to have a conversation with the respondent.

Enumerator introduction

*“Good morning/ afternoon/ Sir/ Madam, My name is (name of enumerator), a field enumerator involved in the **research project** “CITIZEN-SDSS”. The goal of the research project is to support the development of long-term environmental management pathways to sustain local livelihoods in your Barangay and other surrounding areas.*

We are currently in the first phase of the research project. We are conducting this survey to understand your household current livelihood conditions and your perceptions on land quality and ecosystem services. We are further interested to learn how the pandemic influenced your use of natural resources. The information of this survey will be used to provide recommendations for LGUs to improve the quality of local interventions and programmes based on science and research. The main purpose is to support local livelihoods and for nature conversation.

In this regard, I (we) would like to conduct an interview with you. Please, be assured any information of this interview will be treated with privacy. No names of you or your family will be disclosed to government agencies. The information of this interview is used for research purposes only.”

Informed consent

Your participation in this survey is completely voluntary. If you do not want to participate or answer some questions, please inform us immediately. If you feel uncomfortable at some point and do not want to continue, please inform the enumerator. If a particular question is not clear or if you want any further explanation, please feel free to ask.

Your household has been randomly selected for the interview and I would like to know if you are willing to conduct this survey?

Yes=1, No=0	
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If the answer is no, say thank you and proceed with the next pre-selected household.

If the answer is yes, let the respondent sign below, plus providing date, name and location.

Date	Location	Name of respondent	Signature

A. GENERAL INFORMATION

A1. Survey information

1. Name of enumerator:

1.1 First name	1.2 Middle Name	1.3 Last name
2. Date of interview: (mm/dd/yyyy)	3. Time started (hh:mm):	4. Time ended (hh:mm):

A2. Survey review and sanitation

5. Date of checking questionnaire (mm/dd/yyyy):

6. Name of checking person:

	Renz Come	Cecille Mangabat
(yes=1, no=0)		

7. Notes for supervisor in case of missing data, unclear entries (yes=1, no=0):

7.1 Missing data		7.2 Unclear entries	
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8. Date of entering data (mm/dd/yyyy) and uploading to Google drive:

9. Name of checking person and approving data entry:

	Melvin Lippe	Prince Asare
(yes=1, no=0)		

A3. Household head/ interviewed respondent

10. Name of the household head/ primary respondent:

10.1 First name	10.2 Middle Name	10.3 Last name

11. Name of the secondary respondent (if household head is not present):

11.1 First name	11.2 Middle Name	11.3 Last name

12. Cellphone number (if not available=99).

In case of "99", ask to get it from another household member and write down name.

13. Messenger account/ ID (if not available=99).

In case of "99", ask to get it from another household member and write down name.

14. Gender: (1= male, 2= female, 3= prefer not to mention)

15. Are you a member of an indigenous group or tribe?

If yes, please specify.

If household is not a member of such a group/ tribe (enter=2) or (enter=3 if respondent prefer to not mention), proceed to next question.

A4. Location of household

16. Region: (enter=1 for region)

Eastern Visayas		Cagayan Valley	
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17. Province: (enter=1 for province)

Isabela	Cagayan	Southern Leyte

18. Municipality: (enter=1 for municipality)

a. Penablanca	b. Cabagan	c. Tumauni
c. Maasin	d. Silago	e. Others:

19. Name of Barangay:

20. Household address (house no.): (no answer=99)

20.1 House no.	20.2 Sitio	20.3 Zone	20.4 Street

21. Take coordinates (UTM) based on GPS Reading using Smartphone App or GPS.
 (Enumerator: You may need to wait for approx. 5-10 min until accuracy of GPS do not change anymore. Coordinates can be entered at end of interview.)

Latitude (Northing)	Degrees	Minutes	Seconds
Longitude (Easting)	Degrees	Minutes	Seconds

22. Take photosequence of house (ask for consent again) using your smartphone camera:

Consent (yes=1, no=0)	
1.) take photo directing the house entrance, it should <u>include front yard and house borders</u> , 2.) take photo in front of the house <u>towards the left direction of road/ path</u> , 3.) take photo in front of the house <u>towards the right direction of road/ path</u> , 4.) take photo with the house entrance to your back <u>towards the opposite site of the street</u> .	
Enumerator: Photosequences done?	

23. Describe the main access road to the household:

Code list road access (23): 1=Paved Road, 2=one single lane, 3=two lane road, 4=Seasonal Road, 5=Footpath, 6=Others, specify, 99=no answer

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24. Estimate the distance from the household to Barangay hall (using a straight line)?

24.1 Walking distance (minutes)		24.2 Kilometers	
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Code list 25.2**Relationship to household****head (HH)**

- 0 Respondent
- 1 Wife/ Husband
- 2 Son/ Daughter
- 3 Father/ Mother
- 4 Father/ Mother -in-law
- 5 Brother/ Sister
- 6 Son/ Daughter in law
- 7 Stepchild
- 8 Grandchild
- 9 Nephew/ Niece
- 10 Cousin
- 11 Non-related
- 90 Other specify
- 99 **No answer**

Code list 25.8**Reason for joining**

- 1 Founded household
- 2 Marriage
- 3 Born in the household
- 4 Job opportunity
- 5 Job search
- 6 Schooling
- 7 Followed the family
- 8 Came to be looked after (ill, old age, stay alone)
- 9 Came to help household
- 10 Came to live with household due to economic distress
- 11 Came to live with household due to land degradation problems elsewhere
- 12 Came to live with household due to natural disasters
- 13 Religious purposes
- 90 Other specify
- 99 **No answer**

Code list 25.7**Highest level education attainment**

- 1 None
- 2 Primary school incomplete
- 3 Primary school complete
- 4 High school incomplete
- 5 High school complete
- 6 Vocational training incomplete
- 7 Vocational training complete
- 8 University degree incomplete
- 9 University degree complete
- 10 ALS graduate incomplete
- 11 ALS graduate complete
- 90 Others, specify
- 99 **No answer**

Code list 25.9**Occupation**

- 1 None
- 2 Farmer (self-employed)
- 3 Agricultural worker
- 4 Worker (other than agriculture)
- 5 Serviceworker
- 6 Professional in private sector
- 7 Public service
- 8 Self-employed (other than farmer)
- 9 PWD
- 90 Others, specify
- 99 **No answer**

A5. Household composition, education and occupation

25. Who are the members of the household during the past 12 months?

25.0	25.1	25.2	25.3	25.4	25.5	25.6	25.7	25.8	25.9	
ID	Name (First, Middle, Family)	Relation to HH head (code list)	Gender (1=male, 2=female, 3= prefer to not mention)	Age (year)	How long has <i>NAME</i> been living with HH? (year)	Duration of education attainment (Since primary school)? (years)	Highest level education attainment (code list)	Reason for joining (code list)	Occupation during the past 12 months (code list)	
									Primary	Secondary
1										
2										
3										
4										
5										
6										
7										
8										
9										
10										
11										

A6. Pattern of Migration

26. Since when does your household live here?

26.1 Year		26.2 Always lived here? (yes=1, no=0)	
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27. If the household does not originate from the Barangay, when did it migrate to the Barangay?

Year	
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28. Where is HH place of origin in case of moving? (Barangay, Municipality, Province)

28.1	28.2	28.3
Barangay	Municipality	Province

29. What are the 3 most important reasons why the household moved to this Barangay?

29.1		29.2		29.3	
Reason 1		Reason 2		Reason 3	

Code list reason of moving (29.1 to 29.3):

- 1 Work (agriculture-related)
- 2 Work (non-agriculture related)
- 3 Marriage
- 4 Migration of parents, grandparents, relatives
- 5 Overpopulation in place of origin
- 6 No land available for agriculture in place of origin
- 7 Declining soil fertility in place of origin
- 8 High risk of flooding in place of origin
- 9 Other reasons of land degradation in place of origin, specify
- 10 Other natural disasters in place of origin, specify
- 90 Other reasons, specify
- 99 No answer

B. FOREST: MANAGEMENT, ECOSYSTEM SERVICES, CHALLENGES

B1. Forest management

30. Do you **manage parcel/ plots** located in **forest areas**?

If **yes**, fill in table below.

If **no** (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

Code list land use (30.3)

Cropland		Plantations		Other land use types	
1	Permanent cropland	10	Timber tree	31	Aquaculture/ Fishpond,
2	Kaingin (non-permanent)	11	Fruit tree	32	Horticulture commercial
3	Kaingin (permanent)	12	Coconut	33	Homegarden
4	Pasture not-managed	13	Abaca	34	Residential area
5	Pasture managed	14	Banana	90	Other land use, specify
6	Agroforestry	15	Other plantations, specify	99	No answer
7	Fallow				

Code list tenurial instrument (30.4)

1	Part of CBFMA	5	Part of FLGMA	9	Tree farm lease
2	Part of PACBRMA	6	Part of FLMA	10	MOA with farmers (NGP)
3	Part of ISF	7	Part of SFMA	11	Forest without tenure
4	Part of CSC	8	Part of IFMA	12	CLOA
				90	Other, specify
				99	No answer

30.0	30.1	30.2	30.3	30.4
Plot ID	Name of Barangay, Municipality/ City	Area (1 ha=10.000 m ²) (ha)	Land use in 2024 (code list)	Tenurial instrument (code list)
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				

31. Does restricted forest access due to a tenurial instrument has an impact on your household livelihood activities? **(Multiple entries allowed)**

If **yes**, rank their level of impact below and identify tenurial instrument (see code list: 30.4).

If **no** (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question

Code list level of impact (31.1): 99=No answer, 1=Very low, 2=Low, 3=Moderate, 4=High, 5=Very high

		31.1	31.2
ID	Impact restricted forest access on livelihood activities	Level of impact	Tenurial instrument (check code list 30.4)
1	Timber use		
2	Collecting rattan and bamboo,		
3	Collecting foods: honey, mushrooms, edible greens, etc.		
4	Hunting and fishing		
5	Collecting firewood		
6	Collecting deadwood		
7	Collecting other NTFP, specify:		
90	Others, specify		

32. Are you or any of household member involved in forest management activities?

If **yes**, fill in table below and **add HH member ID (Multiple ticks allowed)**.

If **no** (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

		32.1	32.2
ID	Forest management activities	Tick (yes=1, no=0)	HH member ID (check 25.0)
1	Planting of trees		
2	Extension/ education on forest management and protection		
3	Cutting down undesired or competing trees in forest areas		
4	Protecting mothertrees to promote natural regeneration		
5	Harvesting of planted trees		
6	Harvesting of damaged trees after typhoon or storm		
7	Harvesting of deadwood		
8	Protecting forests for drinking and irrigation water provision		
9	Protecting forest areas for wildlife protection		
10	Protecting forest areas for spiritual or religious purposes		
11	Protecting forest areas for ecotourism or recreation		
90	Others (specify)		

B2. Forest ecosystem services

33. Which of the following forest ecosystem services are important for you?

Respondent should rank all. If no (enter=99) to grey box, proceed to next question.

Code list level of importance (33.2): 99=no answer, 1=Not very important, 2=Not important, 3=Intermediate, 4=Important, 5=Very important

		33.2
ID	Forest ecosystem services	Level of importance
1	Air quality	
2	Cooling environment and temperature regulation	
3	Protection from storms and landslides	
4	Maintaining stream and river flow	
5	Providing drinking and irrigation water	
6	Runoff regulation	
7	Soil erosion control	
8	Soil protection	
10	For heritage, cultural, or religious purposes	
11	Recreation	
12	Ecotourism	
90	Others, specify	

34. What products does your household get from the surrounding forest, rank their importance? (Multiple ticks allowed).

If none (enter=99) in box, proceed to next question.

Code list level of importance (34.2): 99=no answer, 1=Not very important, 2=Not important, 3=Intermediate, 4=Important, 5=Very important

		34.1	34.2
Code	Forest benefits	Tick (1=yes, 0=no)	Level of importance
1	Food: fruits, honey, mushrooms, wild plants, etc.		
2	Meat from hunting		
3	Fishing and collecting aquatic animals (frogs, shrimp, etc.)		
4	Timber use		
5	Collecting livestock fodder or feeds		
6	Rattan collection		
7	Bamboo collection		
8	Firewood collection		
9	Charcoal making		
10	Collecting medicinal plants		
11	Collecting ornamentals		
12	Other NTFPs, specify		
90	Others, specify		

37. Where do you collect firewood? (**Multiple answers allowed**).
If no answer provided (enter=99) to grey box, proceed to next question.

ID	Collection area	Tick (yes=1, no=0)
1	Natural forest: by own cutting	
2	Natural forest: collecting fallen branches and deadwood	
3	Timber plantations: by own cutting	
4	Timber plantations: collecting fallen branches and deadwood	
5	Agroforestry: by own cutting	
6	Agroforestry: collecting fallen branches and deadwood	
7	Along streams, river or beaches: collecting deadwood	
8	Along streams, river or beaches: active cutting from growing trees	
8	Inside own farms/ managed areas: collecting deadwood	
9	Inside own farms/ managed areas: by own cutting	
10	Coconut plantations: collecting residues	
11	Nearby house/ residential area: by own cutting	
12	Nearby house/ residential area: collecting wood	
13	Communal woodlots: by own cutting	
14	Communal woodlots: collecting deadwood	
15	Buying firewood from neighbor	
16	Buying firewood from seller	
90	Others, specify	

38. Does your household spend in 2024 (after the pandemic) **more or less** time in collecting firewood compared to 2019 (before the pandemic)?

Code list (38): 1=more, 2=about the same, 3=less, 99= no answer

39. Has the availability of firewood changed in 2024 (after the pandemic) compared to 2019 (before the pandemic)?

Code list (39): 1=declined, 2=about the same, 3=increased, 99= no answer

40. How did your household respond **in case of decline of firewood** availability?

Rank the **5 most important** responses.

Code list level of importance (40): 1=Not very important, 2=Not important, 3=Intermediate, 4=Important, 5=Very important

If no answer (enter=99) to grey box, proceed to next question.

ID	Response	Level of importance
1	Increased collection time as firewood areas is further away from house	
2	Planting of trees on private land	
3	Increased use of agricultural residues as fuel	
4	Increased use of coconut palm leafes	
5	Buying more fuelwood and/ or charcoal	
6	Buying more commercial fuels (kerosene, gas or electricity)	
7	Reduced the needs for use of fuels by using improved stove	
8	More conservative use of fuelwood for cooking and heating	
9	Reduced number of cooked meals	
10	Use of improved technology	
11	Restricting use of firewood	
12	Conserving standings trees for future	
13	Making charcoal	
90	Others, specify	

41. Has your household planted woodlots / fruit trees **on your managed area/ farm** during the past 5 years (before the pandemic)?

If yes, rank 5 most important purposes or reasons.

If no (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

Code list level of importance (41): 1=Not very important, 2=Not important, 3=Intermediate, 4=Important, 5=Very important

ID	Purpose / Reason	Level of importance
1	Firewood for home consumption	
2	Firewood for sale	
3	Livestock fodder for home consumption	
4	Livestock fodder for sale	
5	Timber or poles for own use	
6	Timber or poles for sale	
7	Fruits incl. coffee, cacao for home consumption	
8	Fruits incl. coffee, cacao for sale	
9	Other products for home consumption	
10	Other products for sale	
11	Land demarcation as living fence	
12	To increase value of my land	
13	To allow my children and grandchildren to use these trees	
14	For other environmental services, please specify	
90	Other purposes, specify	

B3. Forest challenges

42. To your knowledge, which of the following activities are legal/ illegal/ require a permit?
(99=no answer). Respondent should answer all activities.

ID	Activities	42.1 Legal (yes=1, no=0)	42.2 Illegal (yes=1, no=0)	42.3 Permit required (yes=1, no=0)
1	Kaingin			
2	Harvesting timber			
3	Collecting firewood			
4	Cutting rattan			
5	Cutting bamboo			
6	Hunting small animals (e.g., birds, lizzards)			
7	Hunting large animals (e.g., deers, pigs)			
7	Fishing (incl. shrimps, snails, frogs)			
8	Harvest of fruits, mushrooms, edible plants			
9	Harvest of wild honey			
10	Harvest of medicinal plants			
11	Collecting other NTFPs			
12	Quarrying (collecting of gravel/ sands)			
13	Expansion of residential areas			
90	Others, specify			

43. Have you observed any of the previously mentioned problems in **forest areas** in your Barangay
(refer to activities listed in question 42)?

If yes, what are 3 most important illegal activities in your opinion?
(1= lowest, 2= moderate, 3= highest).

If no (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

ID Activities (refer to activities listed in question 42 before)	Rank 1 to 3

C. LAND DEGRADATION

44. How does **land degradation influence the land quality** of your Barangay?

If **yes**, what type of land degradation have you **observed?** (**Multiple ticks allowed**).

If **no**, (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to section D.

Code list degradation level (44.2): 99=no answer, 1=Very low, 2=Low, 3=Moderate, 4=High, 5=Very high

		44.1	44.2
ID	Observed land degradation	Tick (yes=1, no=0)	Degradation level
1	Decline of crop production		
2	Increase in weed infestations		
3	Soil erosion		
4	Soil compaction by use of heavy machinery		
5	Soil pollution by chemicals		
6	Overuse of pesticides and herbicides		
7	Decline of soil fertility		
8	Deforestation		
9	Decrease in availability of timber and wood products		
10	Decrease in availability of NTFPs (e.g., edible plants, animals, medicinal plants)		
11	Biodiversity loss: animal species		
12	Biodiversity loss: plant species		
13	Decrease availability of irrigation water		
14	Decrease availability of drinking water		
15	Decrease of water quality		
16	Decrease in groundwater level		
90	Other known land degradation, specify:		

45. What do you think are the main reasons of the observed land degradation? (**Multiple answers allowed**). Name up to 3 per land degradation cause.

If no (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

Code list land degradation reasons (45.1)

Climate change

- 1 Increasing risk of typhoons
- 2 Increasing risk of flooding
- 3 Increasing risk of heat spells
- 4 Increasing risk of droughts
- 5 Increasing risk of forest fires
- 90 Others specify

Natural disasters

- 10 Typhoons
- 11 Flooding
- 12 Droughts
- 13 Pest outbreaks
- 14 Weed infestation
- 90 Others specify

Agricultural practices

- 20 Overuse of fertilizers
- 21 Overuse of pesticides
- 22 Ploughing
- 23 No soil erosion protection
- 24 Overgrazing
- 25 Kaingin
- 90 Others specify

Other reasons

- 30 Uncontrolled local garbage management
- 31 Construction of irrigation channels
- 32 Settlement expansion
- 33 Road construction
- 34 Mismatch between government intervention / programme and local needs to mitigate land degradation
- 35 Domestic in-migration
- 36 Natural conditions of environment: shallow or acidic soils
- 37 Natural conditions of environment: topography or inclination
- 90 Others specify

ID	Land degradation reasons (name the 3 most important ones)	45.1 (Code list)
CC_1	Climate change	
CC_2	Climate change	
CC_3	Climate change	
ND_1	Natural disasters	
ND_2	Natural disasters	
ND_3	Natural disasters	
PAP_1	Poor agricultural practices	
PAP_2	Poor agricultural practices	
PAP_3	Poor agricultural practices	
OTH_1	Other reasons	
OTH_2	Other reasons	
OTH_3	Other reasons	

46. How has land degradation affected your household's livelihood? (**Multiple ticks allowed**).
If no, (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

Code list level of importance (46.2): 99=no answer, 1=Not very important, 2=Not important, 3=Intermediate, 4=Important, 5=Very important

		46.1	46.2
ID	Land degradation effects on livelihoods	Tick (yes=1, no=0)	Level of importance
1	Reduced farming opportunities		
2	Reduced income		
3	Reduced employment opportunities		
4	Reduced access to household		
5	Reduced access to Barangay		
6	Food insecurity		
7	Health problems		
8	Insufficient access to clean drinking water		
9	Insufficient access to irrigation water		
10	Insufficient access to forest timber resources		
11	Insufficient access to non-forest timber resources		
90	Others, specify:		

47. Have you taken **measures to reduce/resolve** any of the observed land degradation?
If yes, what activities do you take to mitigate land degradation? (**Multiple answer allowed**).
If no (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to section D.

ID	Mitigation measures land degradation	Tick (yes=1, no=0)
1	Crop rotation	
2	Cover cropping	
3	Intercropping	
4	Multi-cropping	
5	Use of organic fertilizers	
6	Terracing	
7	Contour plowing	
8	Tree planting	
9	Rotational and controlled grazing	
10	Stop timber poaching from forests areas	
11	Stop extracting firewood from forest areas	
12	Stop extracting NTFPs from forest areas	
90	Others (specify)	

48. Do your household face **challenges** when trying to **reduce or resolve land degradation**?
If yes, rank the challenges below according to importance? (**Multiple ticks allowed**).
If no (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

Code list level of importance (48.2): 99=no answer, 1=Not very important, 2=Not important, 3=Intermediate, 4=Important, 5=Very important

		48.1	48.2
ID	Challenges to resolve/ reduce land degradation	Tick (yes=1, no=0)	Level of importance
1	No knowledge how to mitigate		
2	No support from government agencies		
2a	Training and extension		
2b	Financial support		
2c	In-kind: seedlings, seeds, organic fertilizer		
3	No financial means		
4	No time		
5	No land titling		
6	No technical resources/ machinery		
7	Threatened by illegal loggers		
8	Threatened by people from Barangay		
9	Threatened by people outside Barangay		
90	Others, specify		

**Code list Land use
(49.1 & 49.10 & 49.13)**

- Cropland**
- 1 Permanent cropland
2 Kaingin (non-permanent)
3 Kaingin (permanent)
4 Pasture non-managed
5 Pasture managed
6 **Agroforestry system**
7 Fallow
8 Other cropland, specify
- Plantations**
- 10 Timber tree plantation
11 Fruit tree plantation
12 Coconut plantation
13 Abaca plantation
14 Banana plantation
15 Other plantation, specify
- Forest**
- 20 Natural Forest (Old growth)
21 Secondary Forest
22 Other Forest, specify
- Other land use types**
- 31 Aquaculture/ Fishpond,
32 Horticulture commercial purpose
- 33 Homegarden
34 Residential area/ homestead
90 Other land use, specify
99 **No answer**

Code list ownership (49.3)

- 1 Owned **with** land title
2 Owned **without** title
3 Rented (=Tenant) **with** payment (cash/ in-kind)
4 Rented (=Tenant) **without** payment
5 Renting out as landlord
6 Part of CBFMA
7 Part of PACBRMA
8 Part of ISF
9 Part of CSC
10 Part of FLGMA
11 Part of FLMA
12 Part of SFMA
13 Tree farm lease
14 MOA with farmers (NGP)
15 CLOA
16 Communal land
90 Other type of ownership, specify
99 **No answer**
- Code list mode of acquisition (49.12)**
- 1 Bought
2 Heritage
3 Obtained as a present (e.g., due to marriage)
4 Parcelation
5 Land claimed by forest clearing (kaining)
6 Allocated by government during agrarian reform
7 Allocated by government programme
8 Trade with another land
90 Other mode of acquisition, specify
99 **No answer**

Code list soil fertility (FERT) (49.6)

- 5 Very high
4 High
3 Moderate
2 Low
1 Very low

Code list topography (TOPO) (49.7)

- 5 Very steep
4 Steep
3 Moderate sloping
2 Almost flat
1 Flat

Code list soil erosion potential (ERO) (49.8)

- 5 Very high
4 High
3 Moderate
2 Low
1 Very low

Code list drainage potential (DRAIN) (49.9)

- 5 Very high
4 High
3 Moderate
2 Low
1 Very low

D. LAND USE ASSETS and OWNERSHIP

49. Please indicate the parcels/ plots or area of land (ha) that you currently manage, own, and have rented in/ out?

Note: 1 ha = 10.000 m²; 1 km = 1000 m

If no land parcel is owned, managed or rented in/ out, (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next questions.

49.0 Plot ID	49.1 Land use 2024 (code list) (ask about residential area/ homestead)	49.2 Area of production (ha or m ²) (specify unit!)	49.3 Ownership (code list)	49.4 Distance house to nearest plot border (km or m) (specify unit!)	49.5 Name of Barangay (only if outside study area, name also municipality, if no=99)	49.6 to 49.9 Biophysical Characteristics (“perceived quality of land”) (code list)				49.10 Land use in 2019 (before pandemic) (code list)	49.11 Year of	49.12 Mode of (code list)	49.13 Land use during (code list)
						FERT (49.6)	TOPO (49.7)	ERO (49.8)	DRAIN (49.9)				
1	34												
2													
3													
4													
5													
6													
7													
8													
9													
10													

Code list “agriculture & plantation” land use types (50.1)

<u>Field crops</u>		<u>Plantations</u>		<u>Agroforestry</u>	
1	Paddy rice – rainfed	10	Timber trees	20	Fruit trees and field crops
2	Paddy rice – irrigated	11	Fruit trees	21	Fruit trees and timber trees
3	Upland rice – rainfed	12	Coconut	22	Timber trees and field crops
4	Upland rice – irrigated	13	Abaca	23	Cacao and field crops
5	Corn (Maize)	14	Banana	24	Cacao and fruit trees
6	Sugarcane	15	Pineapple	25	Cacao and timber trees
7	Other field crops, specify	16	Other plantations, specify	26	Coconut and field crops
8	Horticultural crops, specify		<u>Others</u>	27	Coconut and fruit trees
9	Other field crops, specify		Others, specify	28	Coconut and timber trees
		90		29	Homegarden
				30	Other agroforestry, specify

Code list product type

<u>Crops</u>		<u>Trees</u>	
1	Rice unmilled	20	Timber
2	Rice milled	21	Poles
3	Maize comb	22	Fruits
4	Maize grain	23	Other tree products, specify
5	Coconut young (Buko)		
6	Coconut brown (mature)	90	Others specify
7	Coconut dehusked	99	No answer (or not specified)
8	Coconut lumber		
9	Copra		
10	Abaca fibre		
11	Pineapple		
12	Other crop product, specify		

Code list unit

1	Kg
2	Pieces
3	m ² (e.g., board lumber)
4	m ³

E. ECONOMIC AND PRODUCTIVE ACTIVITIES

E1. Income from agriculture & plantation activities (e.g., field crops, plantations: coconut/ fruit/ timber, agroforestry) (Reference period: past 12 months)

50. What are the quantities and values of crops that your household has harvested during the past 12 months?

If HH does **not** own, manage, rent in/ out any plots, (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to question 51.

50.0	50.1	50.2	50.3	50.4	50.5	50.6	50.7	50.8	50.9	50.10
Plot ID	Agriculture /Plantation land use (code list)	Area of production 1 ha= 10.000 m ² (ha / m ²)	No. cropping cycles	Product type ID (code list)	Unit (code list)	Total production (=yield) (50.7 + 50.8) (unit)	Quantity home consumption (incl. as livestock feed) (unit or % total)	Quantity sold (incl. barter / in-kind) (unit or % total)	Price per unit (PHP)	Total value during last 12 months (50.6 * 50.9) (PHP)

51. What are the quantities and values of inputs used in crop production during the past 12 months (refers to agricultural cash expenditures)? (Reference period: past 12 months)

Note 1: Take all agricultural & plantation activities of previous table into account (Question 50).

Note 2: Computation of family labour costs can be based on minimum wage or based on respondent's estimation.

If no answer, (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

51.0 Item ID	51.1 Inputs during past 12 months	51.2 Total quantity during past 12 months	51.3 Unit	51.4 Average price per unit during past 12 months (PHP)	51.5 Subsidised (yes=1, no=0)	51.6 Total costs during past 12 months (51.2 * 51.4; if applicable) (PHP)
1	Rental fees land paid in cash	<i>Not applicable</i>				
2	Seeds		Kg			
3	Fertilizers: sum all kg		Kg			
3	Pesticides: sum all kg		Kg			
4	Pesticides: sum all liter		Liter			
5	Herbicides: sum all kg		Kg			
6	Herbicides: sum all liter		Liter			
9	Draught power by animal	<i>Not applicable</i>				
10	Hired machinery (incl. costs for person who manage machinery)					
11	Transportation & marketing (incl. carrying bags from field, hiring truck)					
90	Other, specify:					
	Labour during past 12 months	51.2	51.3		51.5	51.6 (PHP) (incl. in-kind/barter)
12	Hired labour	<i>Not applicable</i>				
13	Family labour (adult= 100%, child below 18 years =50%)		Person hours	HH member ID (check 25.0):		

Code list livestock, livestock products and aquaculture/ fishing (52.1)

1	Cattle	9	Pig fattening	21	Honey (from bee keeping)
2	Cattle milk	10	Pig fattening meat	22	Fish from sea
3	Cattle meat	11	Piglet	23	Fish from pond
4	Buffalo	12	Piglet meat	24	Fish from river
5	Buffalo milk	13	Duck	25	Other aquatic animals; shrimp, frog, crab, eel, etc.
6	Buffulo meat	14	Duck meat		
7	Goat	15	Duck eggs	90	Other, specifiy
8	Goat meat	16	Native chicken		
		17	Native chicken meat		
		18	Broiler		
		19	Broiler meet		
		20	Chicken eggs		

Code list unit (52.3)

1	Kg
2	Number
3	Living animal

E2. Income from livestock, livestock products, aquaculture/ fishing, incl. bee keeping

(Reference period: past 12 months)

52. Did you have any **income** from livestock, and/or livestock products, aquaculture or fishing **during the last 12 months?**

If **yes**, please list the stocks and livestock products.

If **household did not have any income for E2**, (enter=99) in box, go to next question.

Note 1: Input costs (=major expenses) refer to: feed, veterinary treatment, stocking, slaughterhouse fees, etc.

Note 2: Person hours family labour: adult= 100 %; child= 50 % (age below 18 years)

52.0	52.1	52.2	52.3	52.4	52.5	52.6	52.7	52.8	52.9	52.10
ID	Type of livestock, livestock products, aquaculture/ fishing (Code list)	Quantity (unit)	Unit (code list)	Input costs (non-labour) (PHP)	Hired labour costs (PHP)	Family labour costs (PHP)	HH Member ID for family labour (check 25.0)	Family labour in last 12 months ("sum") (Person hours)	Total sale value (incl. barter / in-kind) (PHP)	Value of home consumption (PHP)
1										
2										
3										
4										
5										
6										
7										
8										

**E3. Income from: Natural resources extracted from forest/ non-forest areas, incl. non-timber forest products (NTFP)
(Reference period: past 12 months)**

Code list Natural resources (incl. forest products) extracted (53.1)

1	Timber	8	Firewood from wood
2	Wild foods: fruits, honey, mushrooms, edible greens, etc.	9	Firewood from coconut materials
3	Meat from hunting	10	Charcoal from wood
4	Fishing and other aquatic animals (shrimp, frog, crabs, etc.)	11	Charcoal from coconut
5	Livestock fodder and feeds	12	Medicinal plants
6	Rattan	13	Ornamentals
7	Bamboo	90	Others, specify
		99	No answer

Code list area of extraction (53.2)

Cropland		Plantations		Forest		Other land use types	
1	Permanent cropland	10	Timber tree	20	Natural Forest (Old growth)	30	Lagoon, Lake
2	Kaingin (non-permanent)	11	Fruit tree	21	Secondary forest	31	River- or streambanks
3	Kaingin (permanent)	12	Coconut	22	Other forest, specify	32	Graslands
4	Pasture natural	13	Abacca		Agroforestry	33	Shrublands
5	Pasture managed	14	Banana	23	Trees with field crops	34	Barren land
6	Agroforestry	15	Other plantation, specify	24	Mixed trees	35	Residential area
7	Fallow land			25	Trees with animals	90	Other, please specify
				26	Trees, field crops, animals		
				27	Homegarden		

53. Did your household **extract natural resources** (timber, NTFP) from forests and non-forest areas, including crop lands, plantations, agroforestry, grasslands, wetlands, etc. and **receive any income**?

If **yes**, please list the products and its quantity, value and costs **during the last 12 months** below.

If **no**, (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next section.

Note 1: Firewood consumption was already asked in questions 35 to 40.

Note 2: Input costs refer to, e.g., use of equipment, fuel costs, etc.

Note 3: Person hours family labour: adult= 100 %; child= 50 % (age below 18 years)

53.0	53.1	53.2	53.3	53.4	53.5	53.7	53.8	53.9	53.10
ID	Type product extracted/ collected (Code list)	Where did you extract natural resource? (Code list)	Input costs (non-labour) (PHP)	Hired labour costs (PHP)	Family labour costs (PHP)	HH Member ID for family labour (Check 25.0)	Family labour in last 12 months ("sum") (Person hours)	Total sale value (incl. in-kind) (PHP)	Value of home consumption (-99 in case of no answer) (PHP)
1									
2									
3									
4									
5									
6									
7									
8									
9									

Code list type occupation (54.2)

- | | | | |
|---|--------------------------|----|---|
| 1 | Agricultural wage labour | 5 | Wage labour in service sector, e.g., waiter, cook, housemaid |
| 2 | Fishermen | 6 | Wage labour in public sector, e.g., policeman, teacher, soldier, local government administration. |
| 3 | Forest guarding | 7 | House construction |
| 4 | Industrial wage labour | 90 | Other, specify |

Code list time unit (54.4)

- | | |
|----|-----------------------------|
| 1 | Day |
| 2 | Month |
| 3 | Year |
| 4 | Lump sum (one time) payment |
| 90 | Other, please specify |

E4. Other sources of income

E4.1 Wage employed activities

(Reference period: past 12 months)

54. Have you or any of your household members worked as a wage-employee in past 12 month? If yes, please fill in table below.

If no answer (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

Note: By wage employed activities, we refer to all activities in the past 12 months, that are not related to agricultural and plantation activities on your own managed area/ farm, e.g., agricultural worker on other farms, factory worker, construction worker, service worker.

54.0	54.1	54.2	54.3 to 54.4		54.5	54.6	54.7
ID Occupation	Household Member ID (Check 25.0)	Type of occupation (Code list)	Net wage in cash (including regular & irregular bonuses)		Value of in-kind benefit received (e.g., food, transportation accommodation etc.) (PHP)	Average number of days worked per month (Days)	Number of months worked during last 12 month (Month)
			Value (PHP)	Time unit (Code list)			
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							
6							
7							
8							
9							
10							

Code list type of business (55.2)

1	Retail-Shop (sales store; Sari-Sari)	8	Agricultural processing	14	Contracted work (cleaning/ maintenance)
2	Petty trader (sales on street)	9	Handicraft	15	Renting out equipment
3	Wholesale	10	Restaurant	16	Hair salon/barber
4	Transport: Tricycle	11	Landlord (farm land)	17	Carpenter
5	Transport: Van	12	Landlord (residential)	19	Bakery
6	Transport: Jeepney	13	Landlord (business)	90	Other, please specify
7	Transport, other specify				

E4.2 Off-farm self-employed/ business activities (Reference period: past 12 months)

55. Have you or any of your household members been involved in any business / off-farm self-employed activities **during the last 12 months?**

If **yes**, please fill in table below.

If **no**, (enter=99) in grey box, go to next question.

Note 1: By non-farm self-employment, we mean you are an own-account worker without employees or have a business with family workers or other employees.

Note 2: If household is involved in several different businesses, fill in one row for each business.

Note 3: Person hours family labour: adult= 100 %; child= 50 % (age below 18 years)

55.1	55.2	55.3	55.4	55.5	55.6	55.7 to 55.8		55.9	55.10
Business ID	Type of business (code list)	Head of business (HH member ID 25.0)	Sale volume / Service revenues (average per month) (PHP)	Cost purchased inputs/ service inputs (average per month) (PHP)	Value of self-produced input/ service (average per month) (PHP)	Cost of labour (average per month) (PHP)		Family labour in last 12 months ("sum") (Person hours)	No. months business operated in last 12 months (month)
						Hired (55.7)	Family (55.8)		
1									
2									
3									
4									
5									
6									
7									
8									

E4.3 Other sources of income (Reference period: past 12 months)

56. Please list any other income that the household received in **the past 12 months**.
If no (enter=99) in bgrey ox, proceed to next question.

ID	Type of income	Total amount received in last 12 months (PHP)
1	Remittances – domestic	
2	Remittances from OFW	
3	Support from government programmes (excluding subsidy for agriculture & plantation activities)	
4	Support from NGOs or similar (incl. in-kind, donations)	
5	Gifts/ support from friends and relatives	
6	Pension	
7	Senior citizen	
8	PWD assistance	
9	Payment for forest patrolling	
10	Payment for renting out land (if in kind, state the equivalent in cash)	
11	Compensation from mining company or similar	
12	Payments from association membership (if in kind, state equivalent in cash)	
13	Insurances	
14	Relief funds	
90	Other, specify: Government study subsidy	
99	No answer	

F. ASSETS and SAVINGS

F1. TYPE of HOUSE

Code list own house (57)

- 1 No
- 2 sole ownership
- 3 sole ownership with other household(s)
- 4 Renting (=tenant) the house alone
- 5 Renting (=tenant) the house with other household(s)
- 90 Other, specify
- 99 No answer

Code list type wall material (58)

- 1 Clay/ Soil
- 2 Wooden (boards, trunks)
- 3 Iron (or other metal) sheets
- 4 Bricks, concrete, blocks
- 5 Fibers/bamboo
- 90 Other, specify
- 99 No answer

Code list type roof material (59)

- 1 Fibers/bamboo
- 2 Wooden (boards)
- 3 Iron or other metal sheets
- 4 Tiles
- 90 Other, specify
- 99 No answer

57. Do you have your own house?

58. What is the type of material of (most of) the walls?

59. What is the type of material of (most of) the roof?

60. How many m² approx. is the **floor house area**? (m²)

F2. ASSETS

61. Please indicate the number and value of implements and other large household items that are **owned** by your household.

If respondent is not willing to share (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

		61.1	61.2	61.3	61.3
ID	Asset	No. of units	Year purchased	Purchasing price per unit (PHP)	Total value today: How much would you "earn", if you sell the asset today? (PHP)
1	Tricycle				
2	Motorbike				
3	Jeepney				
4	Van				
5	Truck				
6	Tractor				
7	e-Bike				
8	Bicycle				
9	Cellphone				
10	Smartphone				
11	TV				
12	Radio				
13	CD/ VCD/ Videoke player				
14	Tablett				
15	Computer / Laptop				
16	Cooking stove (gas / electric)				
17	Refrigerator/ freezer				
18	Fishing boat and boat engine				
19	Chainsaw				
20	Plough				
21	Wooden cart or wheelbarrow				
22	Furniture(s)				
23	Water pump				
24	Solar panel				
90	Others worth more than 3,000 PHP				

F3. SAVINGS and DEBTS (No answer=-99)

- 62. How much does the household have in savings in banks, credit associations, savings groups, etc.? (PHP)
- 63. How much does the household have in savings in non-productive assets such as gold and jewelry? (PHP)
- 64. How much does the household have in outstanding debt? (PHP)
- 65. How much was the household’s loan repayment for the last 12 months? (PHP)
 - 65.1 Payment on principal (PHP)
 - 65.2 Interest payments (PHP)

G. COVID, WELFARE PERCEPTIONS, and SOCIAL CAPITAL

G1. Covid-19 related natural resource extraction

- 66. Did your household increase or decrease its use of natural resource extraction activities during the Covid-19 pandemic (period: 2020-2023) and after 2023 to present.
If no (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

--

Code list frequency (66.1 and 66.2): 1= increased frequency, 2= decreased frequency, 3= no change, 99= no answer

Activity ID	Activity	66.1 Frequency during pandemic (2020-2023) (code list)	66.2 Frequency after pandemic (code list)
1	Harvesting timber		
2	Firewood collection		
3	Food collected from forest areas: Fruits, mushrooms, edible greens, etc.		
4	Food collected from non-forest areas: Fruits, mushrooms, edible greens, etc		
5	Honey collection		
6	Medicinal plant collection		
7	Ornamental plans collection		
8	Bamboo collection		
9	Rattan collection		
10	Other NTFP, specify		
11	Hunting in forest areas		
12	Fishing and collecting aquatic animals (frogs, shrimp, crabs, etc.)		
90	Others, specify		

67. Have you observed any form of deforestation/ forest destruction between 2019 (before pandemic) and 2024 (after pandemic) in **your Barangay or neighbouring Barangay(s)**?

If yes, what are the factors that lead to deforestation? (**Multiple ticks allowed**).
If no deforestation was observed (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

		67.1	67.2
ID	Factors	Tick (yes=1, no=0)	Name of Barangay
1	Timber poaching		
3	Population pressure		
4	Domestic migration		
5	Agricultural land expansion (Kaingin, subsistence purposes)		
6	Agricultural land expansion (Kaingin, commercial purposes)		
7	Lack of awareness environmental impacts by deforestation		
8	Road construction		
9	Lack of law enforcement and monitoring		
10	Uncontrolled settlement expansion		
11	Natural disasters: Typhoons		
12	Natural disasters: Landslides		
13	Natural disasters: Flooding		
14	Natural disasters: Forest fires		
90	Others, specify		

G2. Welfare perceptions and social capital

68. All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life **during the past 12 months**?
If no answer (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

Code list (68): 1=very unsatisfied; 2=unsatisfied; 3=neither unsatisfied or satisfied; 4=satisfied; 5=very satisfied, 99= no answer

69. If you are **“very unsatisfied or unsatisfied”** with your life **during the past 12 months**, provide up to 3 reasons.
If no answer (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

69.1	69.2	69.3
Reason 1	Reason 2	Reason 3

- 70.** Has the household's food production and income over the past 12 months been sufficient to cover the what you consider to be the needs of the household?

Code list (70): 1=no; 2=reasonable (just about sufficient); 3=yes, 99=no answer

- 71.** Compared with other households in your Barangay, how well-off is your household?

Code list (71): 1=worse-off; 2=about average; 3=better-off, 99=no answer

- 72.** How well-off is your household today compared with the situation in 2019 before the pandemic?

Code list (72): 1=less well-off now; 2=about the same; 3=better off now, 99=no answer

- 73. If worse- or better-off:** What is the main reason for the change?
Please rank the **5 most important responses**.

ID	Reason: Change in ...	Rank 1 to 5
1	Wage employment	
2	Land holding (e.g., bought/sold land, eviction)	
3	Using forest resources	
4	Output prices of agricultural products	
5	Outside support (govt., NGO,..)	
6	Remittances	
7	Cost of living (e.g., high inflation)	
8	War, civil strife, unrest	
9	Conflicts in village (non-violent)	
10	Change in family situation (e.g. loss of family member/ major bread-winner)	
11	Illness or being sick	
12	Accessibility (e.g. new road,...)	
13	Increased demand of land area for agricultural production	
14	Decreased demand land area for agricultural production	
15	Religious awakening (i.e., found religion, converted to a new religion)	
16	Started a new business/ lost or less business	
17	Livestock (gain or loss)	
18	Material assets, incl. house (gain or loss)	
90	Others, specify	
99	No answer	

74. Do you have any further issues you like to inform use a or like to talk about? (99=no answer)

H. CHECK LIST ENUMERATOR

- **THANK** the respondent again for their time and willingness to answer our questions.
- Inform the respondent that we will use the provided information for our research analysis and this requires about 12 months to complete. Once we are done, we will report back our results to LGU representatives, and will invite selected members of the Barangay for a feedback workshop.
- Confirm again that names of household members will be **NOT disclosed** to anyone else.
- Did the respondent **SIGN the consent** form already?
- Do you have the full name and **contact details** of the respondent: **phone number** and **messenger ID**? (In case of no phone number or messenger ID, get from another household member)
- Did you already complete the GPS readings of the location of the household?
 - **(GPS app on smartphone or handheld GPS required)**
- Did you already complete the photosequence of the household house and its vicinities?
 - **(Smartphone required)**
- Did you complete the **measurements of firewood consumption** per day?
 - **(Weighing scale and sack required)**
- Did you take a **photo** of the measured **firewood quantity**?
 - **(Smartphone required)**